

Response to preprint review of “The nucleotide binding domain of NRC-dependent disease resistance proteins is sufficient to activate downstream helper NLR oligomerization and immune signaling”

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Response by Mauricio P. Contreras and Sophien Kamoun.

Hi! Thank you for your comments anonymous reviewer!

“The story could be nice, but it is too light.”

That’s a matter of perspective. We do not favor bloated papers with a long list of poorly controlled experiments. Rather, we prefer a focused message with multiple orthogonal experiments. The paper should also be viewed as a follow-up to the influential Moffett et al. (2002) and Rairdan et al. (2008).

“In addition, sentences like “Our results challenge the prevailing paradigm that NLR proteins exclusively signal via their N-terminal domains and reveal a signaling activity for the NB domain of NRC-dependent sensor NLRs.” make me feel like the novelty is “hyped”.

A good number of papers and talks on plant NLRs start with the statement that the N-terminal domains are the signaling domains. Isn’t that what a prevailing paradigm is? Indeed, the Rx-NB result of Rairdan et al. (2008) has somehow been overlooked and is hardly mentioned in the literature even though their finding is robust and has stood the test of time.

“The signaling activity of the NB domain presented here is passive, similar to a guard. The guard model is not novel.”

The guard novel is certainly not novel. We are expanding on this model, and proposing that for sensor-helper NLR pairs in the NRC network, helper NLRs may be guarding sensors as part of their activation mechanism. The reviewer is welcome to point us to an article where the concept of helper NLRs guarding sensor NLRs has been proposed.

“1 Most importantly, interaction data between RxNB (and other NBs) and NRCs should be provided.”

We have discussed this issue in previous papers. Co-immunoprecipitation (CoIP) studies between NRC sensors and helpers have proven notoriously hard to control because of the sticky nature of these interactions. However, we feel like the absence of RxNB signal (and of sensor NLR signal, as per this paper and previous papers (see Contreras et al. 2023 EMBO J, and Ahn et al. EMBO J 2023) suggest that regardless of whether sensor-helper interactions take place, these are transient, and the final helper oligomer does not include the sensor. Perhaps Turbo-ID would be a good tool to study this process! That’s outside the scope of this story though.

“I think the lettuce experiments should be complemented with Q-PCRs to show that defense genes can be upregulated by Rx/NRCs. This should be required before suggesting the use of sensor/helper pair for crop improvement.”

Thanks for the suggestion! We believe cell death is a good proxy for immune activation. See Kourelis et al. 2023, in Science. Regardless, our comments on crop improvement are quite speculative and in the discussion, and no claims are being made regarding crop improvement beyond this speculation. Lettuce experiments are more oriented towards determining if Rx-NRCs are a two component minimal system that can be transferred, akin to Pik1-Pik2 or RGA5/RGA4 from rice. In that sense, we believe the evolutionary distance between Lettuce and *N. benthamiana* provides evidence for this being the case.

"I find it disturbing that the introduction mostly cites previous papers from the Kamoun lab."

Apologies for including too many Kamoun lab references! This story is, in some ways, quite niche and builds on a lot of previous work specifically from our lab.

"I think the use of Rx halves expressed in trans does not bring much to the study and to the understanding of Rx function. Rx full length triggers the same phenotype so why bother using halves? In addition, these halves do not behave like full length Rx in term of oligomerization thus they seem biologically irrelevant."

While qualitatively Rx and Rx halves trigger the same phenotype, our data now provide evidence for the phenotype requiring the same pathways. This is new data. It is true that they behave slightly different in terms of oligomerization, but our focus was mostly on looking at whether they could induce qualitatively similar NRC oligomerization building on the influential study of Moffett et al. 2002. Moreover, the model that inactive Rx halves associate and dissociate upon activation, via conformational changes (see original Moffett et al. 2002 paper) can now perhaps more solidly be linked to NRC activation. Sensor NLR conformational changes leading to NRC activation is perhaps not a ground-breaking concept, but we believe it is something that had not been fully articulated before in the literature, let alone supported with experimental evidence before.

"Figure 1B. Red circle, why not Rx full length in red too?"

Thanks for the suggestion.

"Figure 2 V5 panel is not great. I only see a smear on the whole gel. What is signal, what is noise in this gel? I don't think we can conclude anything from this. Plus, why should we care about what this chimeric truncation of a protein does?"

Lack of clear distinguishable signal in V5 panel is in itself an observation. Of course it is hard to conclude much, but at least we can say that unlike full-length Rx, it appears the Rx halves expressed *in trans* exist in multiple different conformations, with perhaps the LRR forming aggregates, as discussed in the results. The reason why we care about this split protein (not chimeric), which perhaps was not well articulated in the manuscript, is that it was the foundation for an influential model for NLR activation that proposed that conformational changes were at the root of activation (see Moffett et al. 2002, EMBOJ). We are now trying to link those conformational changes in the sensor (which do not lead to sensor resistosome assembly) to activation of helper NLRs (which do form resistosomes).

“Figure 3D: Why use time point? There is no difference between 3/4/5dpi. Most importantly, where are eGFP and CP-GFP?”

We included timepoints because we were interested in comparing the efficiency of RxNB and Rx/CP activation of NRC2, which appears to be different. RxNB activation of NRC2 at 3dpi still showed some signal corresponding to the inactive state. Interestingly this signal is still there even at 5dpi. We'll clarify this logic a bit more in the results. eGFP and CP-GFP are visible in the accompanying SDS-PAGE blots. eGFP is too small and often migrates off the gel in BN-PAGE. CP-eGFP accumulates relatively weakly and is trickier to detect in BN-PAGE than in SDS-PAGE, mainly because you have to load less sample for BN-PAGE gels than in SDS-PAGE gels. Regardless, our conclusions are not affected by the absence of these proteins on the BN-PAGE blots.

“Figure 4 is nice; I like this part. I would like to have the WB data in the main figure, it would be easier to read (to understand that accumulation is correlated to activity). However, this part could really benefit from protein interaction data.”

This is something we considered! Maybe we can revisit this option. We felt that WB data would make the figure too cluttered, but perhaps we can rearrange things to include the WB as main. We'll think about this further!

“Figure 5: The chlorosis symptoms on the adaxial part of the leaves are not clear. You should remove this and keep only the abaxial pictures to avoid misleading the readers.”

Good suggestion. Adaxial should be included as supp to be transparent about the phenotype.

“Figure 6: This schematic is not great. Is the p-loop required for Rx activation or for NRC activation? Is it even a 2step process? Isn't it just that CP activates NRCs by changing Rx conformation?”

The schematic proposed is a working model, intended to help the reader understand our hypotheses and data more clearly. The p-loop is required for both. Rx activation is NRC activation, as NRCs are genetically downstream. We have no evidence for constitutive interaction between Rx and NRCs prior to activation, therefore we decided to start with Rx being separate from NRC2. As mentioned above, based on our lettuce experiments, the p-loop independency of RxNB-eGFP, the lack of Rx or RxNB-eGFP signal matching the NRC2 oligomer, and the lack of a shift in size in the NRC2 oligomer when activating with Rx or RxNB-eGFP, we think that Rx activation leads to a transient, direct interaction, hence why we illustrated it as a 2-step process. The model we propose, in which helpers sense conformational changes in sensors, has not to our knowledge been proposed before.

“What do we know about Rx halves interacting together?”

Rx halves have already been reported to associate. See Moffett et al. 2002 EMBO J. Hence why we illustrated them together.

“The structure of the NRC resistosome is unknown, membrane insertion is unknown but here these are presented as facts.”

While the NRC2 structure is unknown, based on BN-PAGE and gel filtration assays (See Contreras et al. 2023 EMBO J), we have evidence for it being an NRC homo-oligomer that matches the size of a pentamer, or perhaps even a hexamer, similar to ZAR1 and Sr35. Based on the conservation of pentameric resistosome assemblies in Sr35 and ZAR1 (monocot and dicot CC-NLRs respectively), we believe that all the evidence points to an analogous homo-oligomerization mechanism. In this same paper (Contreras 2023 EMBO J), we also presented evidence for membrane localization and association for the activated NRC2 oligomers.

I hope this helps. Good luck with the publication!

Thank you for taking the time to submit a public review!